

Intercontinental optical clock comparison using the geodetic VLBI technique in K-band

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Overview

- Why to compare clocks
- How to compare clocks: different methods
- Italy-Japan VLBI clock comparison
- Italy-Korea VLBI clock comparison (K-band)
- Future perspectives (CTR)

Why to compare clocks

- Optical clocks are the state of art in time-and freq metrology
- Used for redefining the SI second

Clock Metrology

European fibre link network

Why to compare clocks

- Optical clocks are the state of art in time-and freq metrology
- Used for redefining the SI second
- Also absolute height measurements: chronometric levelling

Relativistic Geodesy

Grotti et al., Nature Phys 14, 2018

Mehlstaebler et al. 2018 Rep. Prog. Phys. 81 064401

Why to compare clocks

- Optical clocks are the state of art in time-and freq metrology
- Used for redefining the SI second
- Also absolute height measurements: chronometric levelling
- Study the variation of physical constants (e.g. fine structure constant)

How to compare clocks

M. Sekido (2012)

Clock comparison methods

- Optical fibres (short-medium distances up to 2000 km)
- GNSS techniques (GPS-IPPP): reliable/cheap but slow
- Two-Way Satellite Time and Frequency transfer: reliable, precise but expensive (rented sat time $\sim 200\text{kUSD/yr}$)
- Very Long Baseline Interferometry: metrology chain w station H-masers \rightarrow reliable and more precise than GPS

ITA-JPN Broadband VLBI Experiment for Optical Clock Comparison

Medicina 2.4m

Kashima 34m

Koganei 2.4m

- Broadband 2.4m GALA-V System for Ytterbium-Strontium optical frequency comparison

Italy-Japan optical clock comparison

- 10 observing sessions: 3x60 Tby per session
- correlation performed in Japan (NICT)

- Node-Hub style VLBI scheme: Closure delay relation used to derive delay between 'small-small' baseline
- Results of the 2018-2019 campaign in Pizzocaro+2021, Sekido+ 2021

- VLBI chain:
 $y(\text{Yb}/\text{Sr}) = 2.5(2.8) \times 10^{-16}$
(VLBI contribution= 9×10^{-17})
- GPS-IPPP chain:
 $y(\text{Yb}/\text{Sr}) = -3.2(4.0) \times 10^{-16}$
(IPPP contribution= 2.6×10^{-16})

Italy-Korea VLBI clock comparison

Goals in 2021-2022

Frequency transfer scheme

- First experiment: 16-17 Dec 2021
- Six antennas involved: Medicina, Sejong, Tamna, Ulsan, Yonsei, Yebeo
- 24h K-band geodetic session (450 scans)
- Data transferred and correlated both in Bologna and KASI
- Data analysis performed in nuSolve and VieVS (for iono correction)

VLBI Correlation in Bologna

- DiFX (Deller+2007) correlator VLBI-IT since 2012 (FP7-NEXPreS project)
- System based on four (in the future six) nodes linked by Infiniband net at 40 Gb/s
- Storage: 110 Tby per node (read in parallel by each antenna)
- Every node connected to GARR at 10 Gb/s via dedicated connection
- Real time correlation of 4 antennas at 2 Gb/s possible
- Standard mode of ops: storage of VDIF or Mark-5 data and offline correlation
- Used for correlation of radio astronomy and geodetic observations
- Italian antennas frequently joined by other countries (Spain, Poland, Korea, South Africa)

Italy-Korea VLBI clock comparison

Medicina H-maser connected to INRiM Ytterbium optical clock via Italian Quantum Backbone fiber link

Sejong H-maser connected to KRISS Ytterbium clock via KISTI fiber link

Data correlated using Bologna DiFX software correlator
Resulting database 21DEC16XF analysed with nuSolve

Group delay residuals: wrms = 24.9 ps (3313/6010 used/tot pairs)

Sejong-Medicina clock rate: CL1 = $(-21.484 \pm 0.138) \times 10^{-14}$ s/s

Preliminary results!

Future perspectives

Compact Triband Rx VLBI-OCC Campaign

- Compact Triband Rx (CTR) in Medicina and Yonsei for OCC campaign
- Optimal frequency set-up (18-116 GHz)
- Target sources from ICRF3 based on telescope sensitivity
- Schedule done with `sur_sked` (`VieSched++` used for simulations)
- Data transfer via dedicated link at high speed
- Correlation w/ upgraded Bologna correlator and Korean Nat'l supercomputer
- Data analysis in `VieVS` (Boehm+ 2018) or `PIMA` (Petrov+ 2011):
iono corrections from IGS Global Ionospheric Maps
- GPS-IPPP commensal campaign

Ultimate Goal

VLBI-based optical clock comparison

- 10^{-17} or better clock comparison on intercontinental scale
- Regular contribution to UTC after redefinition

Optical-clock-based geodetic VLBI

- Broadband high-frequency geodesy
- Improve reference frames with SLR

Thank you for your attention

Stadtpfarrkirche Mariä Himmelfahrt